

First steps towards building a dictionary of emotional requirements in healthcare and well-being

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Abstract—Emotional requirements represent how a user should feel when interacting with a software-intensive system. Eliciting and addressing these requirements during the early phases of the system design is essential for a successful system as it improves the system’s acceptance. However, this is not an easy task because stakeholders express their desired emotional requirements using very different terminology and expressions, which may result in confusion and inconsistency between what a stakeholder says and what a requirements engineer understands. Specifically, there is a lack of a well-defined approach to understand and elicit such requirements. This paper aims to solve this problem by developing a prototypical dictionary of emotional requirements that offers a clear and organized set of terms, which can be used to properly elicit stakeholders’ emotional requirements considering the healthcare and well-being domain as a disclosure domain.

Index Terms—Emotions, Affects, Emotional requirements, Requirements engineering, Software engineering

I. INTRODUCTION

Emotional requirements represent how a user should feel when interacting with a software-intensive system [1]. For example, a patient should feel *capable* of managing her or his health by means of the e-healthcare system [2]. Emotional requirements can be both positive and negative in the sense that while a positive emotional requirements represents how the user should feel, a negative emotional requirement expresses the opposite – how the user is not supposed to feel. For example, a patient should not feel nervous when managing his or her health by means of the e-healthcare system. Eliciting emotional requirements of end users and considering them during the early phases of the system design is essential for a successful software-intensive system as it improves the system acceptance [3]. On the contrary, not giving adequate consideration to such requirements may result in a system that does not offer essential features that are required by its users, which will hinder the system adoption by users for whom it has been developed [4].

Accordingly, emotional requirements are of significant importance for healthcare and well-being systems, where user acceptance and adoption are essential.

Several studies have considered emotional requirements for healthcare and well-being systems. For instance, emotional requirements were considered for a clinical prediction tool (CPT) to identify those at risk of persistent depression, specifically, in general practice waiting rooms [5]. Alkhomsan and others [6] studied emotional requirements during the COVID-19 pandemic for virtual clinic applications that allow users to access and obtain medical e-services, in contrast to traditional in-person visits. Another example is the consideration of emotional requirements for intervention solutions that contribute to fighting against low physical activity levels among adolescents [1].

Among a number of studies concerned with emotional requirements (e.g., [1]–[3], [5], [7]–[14]), only a few of them offer structured approaches or frameworks, such as [14], [15], for eliciting and representing emotional requirements. This has been confirmed by our recent experience in the PHArA-ON project¹ that is aimed at making smart and active living a reality for Europe’s elderly population [16], [17].

On the other hand, dealing with emotional requirements is complex because stakeholders express the desired emotional requirements using very different terminology and expressions, which may result in confusion and inconsistency between what a stakeholder says and what a requirements engineer understands. Consequently, a major problem in eliciting emotional requirements is the lack of agreed-upon terminology, which is required to facilitate the elicitation and specification of such requirements.

Specifically, emotional requirements cover a wide

¹<https://www.pharaon.eu/>

range of needs, which are frequently more subjective and difficult to measure [10]. In this context, without a well-defined approach for dealing with emotional requirements, it is almost impossible to properly understand, elicit, and validate emotional requirements as well as compare and reuse them across different software projects.

The healthcare and well-being domain is no exception, i.e., there is a lack of comprehensive terminology to describe emotional requirements. This hinders effective communication and understanding among stakeholders. Consequently, there is a critical need to develop a dictionary of emotional requirements that provides descriptions of emotional requirements relevant to healthcare and well-being, thereby facilitating improved communication, research, and development of emotional interventions in this domain. The dictionary should be prototypical in the sense that the actual meaning of the words and expressions referring to emotions in emotional requirements vary from person to person and from one context to another. Without a prototypical dictionary of emotional requirements, requirements engineers and developers may struggle to accurately capture and address the emotional needs of end users, leading to sub-optimal user experiences.

In this paper, we aim to solve the research problem by presenting the first steps towards building a prototypical dictionary of emotional requirements for the healthcare and well-being domain. The dictionary has been constructed by first identifying relevant studies in both top-tier requirements engineering (RE) and software engineering (SE) journals and conferences as well as some other sources. These studies were further analyzed to derive key emotional requirements, their example definitions, and how they can be categorised for the construction of the dictionary. Our study is the first study of its kind according to the best of our knowledge.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the research background, and Section III describes the design of the study. Section IV reports on the results of the study. In Section V, we provide an overall discussion of the study and present and discuss the threats to validity. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and discusses future work.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Emotion theories

Different emotion theories have been proposed to understand the origin and distribution of emotion categories. These theories include theory of basic emotions [18], [19], appraisal theory [20], [21], and constructed emotion theory [22], [23]. Although these theories offer different categorizations of emotions and all of them agree that emotions can and need to be categorised,

they also agree that some emotions do not easily fall under any of the proposed categories, including “feeling of assurance” [12], “sense of ownership” [2], [5], and “sense of loneliness” [10], [24]. As there is no shared agreed-upon categorization of emotions, we will proceed with the bottom-up approach where we first analyze the research literature about the instances of emotional requirements and then try to categorize them by ourselves based on the current understanding of emotion categories. In the following subsections II-B, II-C and II-D, we will provide an overview of how the understanding about emotion categories has evolved.

B. Innate emotion categories

According to basic emotion theories [19], emotions are natural categories whose instances share a physical fingerprint, such as a set of facial movements (an expression) and a pattern of autonomic nervous system activity. Basic emotion theories also claim that there exists a set of innate discrete emotions shared among different organisms that appear to be similar and comparable across different cultures and societies. A well-known proponent of the theories of basic emotion Paul Ekman [18] claims that the six basic emotion categories are anger, disgust, fear, happiness, sadness, and surprise. However, scientists have not been able to agree on which emotions are basic or innate categories [20]. Also, instances of an emotion category can vary in their affective features [25]. For example, some instances of fear can be pleasant, and some instances of happiness can be unpleasant [26].

C. Prototypical emotion categories

Proponents of prototypical emotion categories [21], [27]–[30] claim that instances of emotion categories vary a lot but each emotion category has a typical or frequent instance or *prototype*. Such *prototype* possesses a common set of features, and instances of an emotion category are graded in their similarity to the prototype [25]. However, the empirical evidence indicates that the instances of an emotion category vary more substantially in their features than can easily be accounted for by a prototype approach [31]. For example, a recent meta-analysis [32] identified weak reliability in the facial movements that adults use to express emotions.

D. Constructed emotion categories

Based on recent findings and advances in neuroscience [22], [23], emotion categories are abstract categories whose instances support the functional goal to be achieved [23]. For example, according to [25], in situations involving competition or negotiation, instances of the ‘anger’ emotion category might be constructed such that they support the attainment of the functional

goal to win [33], while in situations of threat, the anger category might support achieving the functional goal to overcome an obstacle [34], [35].

In other words, emotion categories like fear, anger, cool, fun and happiness are not in-built; they are learned and constructed by individuals as abstract categories despite a wide range of variation in the features of their instances. Children learn emotion categories by means of emotion words, which are used by parents or caregivers in a particular social context. For example, learning that a heavy sigh or widened eyes by a caregiver, associated with the word “angry”, are followed by decreased touch and attention will encourage the infant brain to develop a situation-specific ‘anger’ emotion category [35].

It is worthwhile to emphasize that an emotion category is learned despite, and perhaps even because of, variable patterns of facial movements, vocal cues, actions, and sensory data from the body of an individual and the surrounding external context on one hand, and predictable functional outcomes in a given situation [25]. In short, an emotion category is an abstraction that need not exist in nature (as is true for any biological category) [22].

Based on the preceding discussion, we can state that it is not possible to categorize emotions included by emotional requirements based on some *a priori* existing categorization of emotions. Instead, we should categorize emotional requirements according to the domains and situations to which they apply, also considering variability how emotions are perceived by different end users and other stakeholders in different contexts. This will be done in the rest of this paper.

E. Affects

At a basic level, emotions are formed from simpler feelings known as basic affects [36]. Two characteristics can be used to characterize affects: valence, indicating how pleasant or unpleasant one feels, and arousal, indicating how excited or calm one feels. Detecting affects is facilitated by psychological tests or physiological measures, such as heart rate, which can indicate excitement. Emotions can also be characterized in terms of their valence and arousal, which arise from the valence and arousal of their core affects [36], [37]. Valence and arousal values can be assigned to words denoting emotions [38], using for this purpose a method like the one described in [39], [40].

III. STUDY DESIGN

A. Research questions

The purpose of our research work was to take first steps towards composing a dictionary of emotional requirements by identifying instances of emotional requirements from the research literature concerned with requirements engineering and software engineering. The

research questions (RQs) have been designed with the objective of identifying key emotional requirements, their definitions, and how they can be categorised in the healthcare and well-being domain:

- **RQ1:** What are the most common emotional requirements, both positive and negative, observed in the healthcare and well-being domain?
- **RQ2:** How are the identified emotional requirements defined in the healthcare and well-being domain?
- **RQ3:** How to categorise emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain?

B. Research method

We aimed to identify instances of emotional requirements in leading RE and SE conferences and journals. Accordingly, our research method followed the methodology applied in similar works in SE [41]–[43]². Our research method consists of two phases: *Publication search* and *Publication selection*:

1) *Publication search:* We conducted a three-step search for relevant publications to identify instances of emotional requirements in healthcare and well-being. These steps involved publication sources search, applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, and duplicates’ removal, which are elaborated below:

Publication sources search: We selected several publication sources for our search, which are generally considered to be the top RE and SE journals, and some top journals on information systems (IS). We further selected top conference proceedings concerned with requirements and software engineering. We expanded other publication search by considering other valuable sources focused on emotional requirements, healthcare, and well-being. Table I shows the list of our search sources.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria: After downloading all available publications from the publication sources considering the period from 2018 to 2023, we established a set of criteria for publication inclusion and exclusion. The applied selection criteria are presented in Table II. According to the criteria, we incorporated full research articles released from 2018 to 2023 as we were willing to ensure that the selected studies were recent and relevant to current research trends in RE, focusing on the healthcare and well-being domain.

²The study companion materials (e.g., a dictionary of emotional requirements, identified studies, selected studies, etc.) can be found in <https://figshare.com/s/2157ec77368101fca058>

TABLE I
SEARCH SOURCES

No. Top journals	Total
1. Journal of Systems and Software (JSS) ³	1142
2. Requirements Engineering (REJ) ⁴	136
3. Information and Software Technology (IST) ⁵	906
4. Empirical Software Engineering (ESE) ⁶	814
5. Information Systems Journal (IS) ⁷	213
6. IEEE Transactions of Software Engineering (TSE) ⁸	799
Top conferences	
1. IEEE International Conference on Requirements Engineering (RE) ⁹	231
2. International Working Conference on Requirements Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality (REFSQ) ¹⁰	125
3. International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE) ¹¹	940
4. International Symposium on Empirical Software Engineering and Measurement (ESEM) ¹²	195
5. European Software Engineering Conference and Symposium on the Foundations of Software Engineering (ESEC/FSE) ¹³	710
6. International Conference on Cooperative and Human Aspects of Software Engineering (CHASE) ¹⁴	113
Other sources	
1. International Workshop on Affective Computing in Requirements Engineering (AffectRE) ¹⁵	24
2. International Workshop on Requirements Engineering for Well-Being, Aging, and Health (REWBAH) ¹⁶	31
3. Emotions in Requirements Engineering: A Systematic Mapping Study (SLR) [44]	26
	6,405

Our criteria involve deselecting the editorial boards for all our journals. When searching issues of the JSS journal, we deselected the editorial board before downloading chosen articles monthly and exporting their abstracts in the BibTeX format. We applied the same procedure to the IST, ESE, IS, and TSE journals. We also excluded keynotes, panel papers, doctoral symposium papers, posters, and tool demos from the RE conference. Short papers and vision papers were excluded from the REFSQ and ICSE conferences along with keynotes

³<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-systems-and-software>

⁴<https://link.springer.com/journal/766>

⁵<https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/information-and-software-technology>

⁶<https://link.springer.com/journal/10664>

⁷<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/13652575>

⁸<https://www.computer.org/csdl/journal/ts/2023/02>

⁹<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/1000630/all-proceedings>

¹⁰<https://link.springer.com/conference/refsq>

¹¹<https://dl.acm.org/conference/icse/proceedings>

¹²<https://dl.acm.org/doi/proceedings/10.1145/3239235>

¹³<https://dl.acm.org/conference/fse/proceedings>

¹⁴<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/1814404/all-proceedings>

¹⁵<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/1828005/all-proceedings>

¹⁶<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/10260706/proceeding>

TABLE II
INCLUSION AND EXCLUSION CRITERIA OF RESEARCH ARTICLES

I/E	No	Criteria
I	1	Include full research articles published between 2018 and 2023.
E	2	Exclude tables of contents, editorials board, keynotes, panel papers, doctoral symposium, posters and tool demos, short papers, vision papers, extended abstracts, and duplicate articles.

and extended abstracts. From the ESEM conference, we excluded vision papers, posters, and short papers. From the ESEC/FSE conference, we excluded keynotes, short papers, ideas, visions, and reflections, as well as demonstrations and student research competitions. From the CHASE conference, we excluded posters and demos. **Duplicates' removal:** After identifying 6,405 publications from all sources, we removed 17 duplicate papers as is reflected by Figure 1.

2) *Publication selection:* The publishing selection procedure consisted of two steps: title and abstract selection and quality assessment, discussed as follows:

Title and abstract selection: In this phase, we followed the approach that has been put forward by Perera et al [41] since they stated that abstract-based classification is widely accepted in the SE research literature. Consequently, a comprehensive examination of the titles and abstracts of the studies was conducted, as a result of which 93 studies were selected out of the initially found 6405 studies.

Quality assessment: Although using title and abstract selection can reduce the noise by excluding non-relevant publications, it neither guarantees that the selected studies are of high quality nor they are relevant to our research. Accordingly, to find high-quality papers that include instances of emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain, we have defined four quality assessment (QA) criteria to assess the quality of the papers. The QA criteria are shown in Table III, and are discussed in the following paragraphs.

QA1 assesses whether the study focuses primarily

TABLE III
QUALITY ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

QA	Description
QA1	Is the content of the work concerned with emotional requirements?
QA2	Are instances of emotional requirements discussed within the methodology, results, or discussion?
QA3	Does the content propose or develop software solutions specifically tailored for the healthcare and well-being domain?
QA4	Does the study consider a healthcare professional and/or a patient as the end-user(s)?

on emotional requirements rather than functional and quality (i.e., nonfunctional) requirements. QA2 assesses whether the study contains concrete contributions relevant to emotional requirements rather than ideas and preliminary work. This is crucial because multiple papers that were considered only described instances of emotional requirements in their introduction or research background sections, rather than in the research methodology, results, or discussion sections. QA3 assesses whether the contribution of the study has been applied rather than just proposing theoretical ideas related to healthcare and well-being. Finally, QA4 assesses whether the emotional requirements in the study are concerned with at least one of the two key roles of concern, which are healthcare professional and patient. The purpose of QA4 is to exclude studies that consider the requirements concerned with software developer or any other role that is not relevant for our study.

A paper must meet all four QA criteria to be considered, and applying the QA criteria to the 93 studies resulted in the selection of 21 papers. A simplified representation of the search and selection of the papers is shown in Fig. 1.

C. Method of categorizing emotional requirements

As we stated in subsection II-E, emotions can be categorized according to their valence and arousal values [36], [37], which can also be assigned to words denoting emotions [38]. This has been done by means of methods like the one described in [39], [40], which has resulted in emotion lexicons, such as the ones described in [45]–[47]. The most extensive of these emotion lexicons is the NRC-VAD lexicon [47]¹⁷. We therefore used the NRC-VAD lexicon in our research, by determining the valence and arousal values of the emotion words and phrases that had been used for expressing instances of emotional requirements discovered in the research literature. We claim that such values characterize abstract emotion categories [22] referred by the requirements’ instances.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we present the findings of our study. Next, we will provide answers to the research questions RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3 that were posed in subsection III-B.

A. RQ1. *What are the most common emotional requirements, both positive and negative, observed in the healthcare and well-being domain?*

In the selected 21 studies, we elicited 61 instances of emotional requirements. The results include 41 positive emotional requirements and 20 negative emotional requirements.

Fig. 1. Search and selection process of selected papers

Fig. 2 illustrates the frequency of positive emotional requirements identified in our study. The emotional requirements Empowered, Sense of ownership, Confident, and Connected have the highest occurrence, each appearing four times. The emotional requirements In control, Cared for, and Motivated have appeared three times and Hopeful, Private, Comfortable, Empathetic, Involved, Professional, Satisfied, Capable, Informed, and Relaxed have appeared two times. The rest of the positive emotional requirements have appeared only once, namely: Excited, Clear, Respected, Helpful, Supportive, Authoritative, Listened to, Resilient, Discrete, Not perplexed, Organized, Beneficial, Calm, Fun, Secure, Pleasurable, Independent, Dignified, Not overloaded, Enjoyable, Reassuring, Relieved, Safe, and Cautious.

Figure 3 illustrates the frequency of negative emotional requirements identified in our study. The emotional requirement Fearful has the highest occurrence, as it has appeared six times. The emotional requirements Frustrated and Anxious have appeared five times, and Worried has appeared four times. Moreover, Shameful and Lonely have appeared three times, and Confused has appeared twice. The rest of the negative emotional requirements have appeared only once, namely: Burned out, Regretful, Discriminating, Overwhelmed, Nervous,

Fig. 2. Frequency of positive emotional requirements

¹⁷<https://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/nrc-vad.html>

Fig. 3. Frequency of negative emotional requirements

Threatened, Lack of belonging, Insecure, Inattentive, Angry, Annoyed, Disappointed, and Bored.

B. RQ2. *How are the identified emotional requirements defined in the healthcare and well-being domain?*

After identifying the 61 emotional requirements, we have extracted their various definitions from the relevant studies. These definitions are listed in Table IV in Figshare¹⁸.

C. RQ3. *How to categorise emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain?*

By following the principles described in subsection III-C, we categorized the identified instances of emotional requirements by the valence and arousal values of the emotion words and phrases referred by the emotional requirements that were discovered with the help of the NRC-VAD lexicon [47]¹⁹.

Fig. 4 shows how the identified instances of emotional requirements have been mapped to the valence and arousal values of the corresponding to the requirements emotion words and phrases. The figure shows four clearly distinguishable groups of emotional requirements. The largest group is formed by the positive emotional requirements with low arousal and low valence. This is followed by the negative emotional requirements with high arousal and low valence. The third group is positive emotional requirements with high arousal and high valence and the smallest group is composed of negative emotional requirements with low arousal and low valence.

V. DISCUSSION

In this section, we will look deeper into the results presented in Section IV.

Our research question RQ1 focuses on the most frequent emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain. An intriguing finding is that the emotional

requirements Empowered, Sense of ownership, Confident, and Connected appeared in the studied publications four times each. This may indicate the significance of these emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain. This finding may be interpreted in the way that when people feel empowered to make decisions with the support of information technology, they are more likely to feel ownership over their health data, feel confident in utilizing the technology, and feel connected to others. On the other hand, Fearful is the most frequently mentioned negative emotional requirements in the studied publications, despite the fact that information technology, such as e-healthcare systems, have been designed with the objective of reducing fear in mind. This indicates the significance of the emotion of fear in the healthcare and well-being domain and the need to further deal with it.

Regarding RQ2, when there were multiple definitions for an emotional requirement, we presented all of them in Table IV in Figshare²⁰. An emotional requirements can have several definitions because, as we stated in subsection II-D, emotions vary according to the domains and situations to which they apply. Therefore, there can be no *a priori* stated "legal" definition for any emotional requirement.

Concerning RQ3, we used the NRC-VAD lexicon [47]²¹ for categorizing the identified instances of emotional requirements by the valence and arousal values of the emotion words and phrases corresponding to the emotional requirements. We discovered that instances of emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain frequently had a high valence and low arousal. This could be because individuals who are not physically or mentally well frequently benefit from interventions that induce a low arousal state to aid in their recovery process. Healthcare and well-being technology can play an important role in offering such interventions to improve people's mental health and well-being.

However, the categorization of emotional requirements by valence and arousal with the help of the NRC-VAD lexicon may not accurately reflect the complexities of emotions in the healthcare and well-being domain because such values characterize abstract [22] rather than concrete emotion categories of the requirements' instances. Considering this, the valence and arousal values identified by means of the NRC-VAD lexicon may need to be adjusted for the healthcare and well-being domain. In particular, we do not agree with some of the valence and arousal values assigned to the relevant emotion words and phrases in the NRC-VAD lexicon, such as the values for the emotion words Confident and

¹⁸<https://figshare.com/s/2157ec77368101fca058>

¹⁹<https://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/nrc-vad.html>

²⁰<https://figshare.com/s/2157ec77368101fca058>

²¹<https://saifmohammad.com/WebPages/nrc-vad.html>

Fig. 4. Distribution of the identified instances of emotional requirements along the valence and arousal dimensions

Fearful shown in Figure 4. Our expectation was that Confident should have a high arousal and high valence instead of a low arousal and high valence. This is due to the fact that feeling confident in using healthcare and well-being technology requires self-assurance.

Also, it was surprising to discover that Fearful had been assigned in the NRC-VAD lexicon with a low arousal and low valence, as is shown in Figure 4. Typically, fear is associated with a high arousal and low valence, manifested by an increased heart rate and adrenaline release, in response to perceived threats or dangers [48]. We can conclude that the emotion of feeling fear should be more precisely categorized for the healthcare and well-being domain.

Emotion words and phrases corresponding to some instances of emotional requirements, such as Not perplexed, Not overloaded, and Inattentive, are not included in the NRC-VAD lexicon. However, emotion words corresponding to their opposites, Perplexed, Overloaded, and Attentive, are included. To address this gap, we reversed the arousal and valence values of the opposites to estimate the missing values.

Our results serve as a useful point of reference for other researchers and practitioners dealing with requirements engineering for the healthcare and well-being domain. Our mapping of the identified from the literature emotional requirements to their arousal and valence values represents the patterns of emotional requirements

in healthcare and well-being. While our results cover only a limited set of examples of possible emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain, they offer a starting point for selecting and fine-tuning them for each actual case and problem at hand.

Comprehensive dataset of the study can be accessed through Figshare²².

A. Threats to validity

In this section, we present and discuss the threats to the validity of our work:

- **Selection bias in potential studies** is a prevalent concern in this type of research, indicating a tendency to report positive findings over negative ones. Our investigation focused on identifying pertinent research on emotional requirements in healthcare and well-being, with no predisposition toward positive or negative outcomes. Nonetheless, we meticulously established inclusion and exclusion criteria to guide our search and selection process for relevant studies.
- **Authors' background.** The authors' expertise lies in requirements engineering, potentially impacting their approach to searching and selecting relevant studies, as they might lean towards studies that they are more familiar with. However, to mitigate this

²²<https://figshare.com/s/2157ec77368101fca058>

influence, we adhered to a widely recognized and adopted study protocol.

- **Completeness.** Ensuring completeness in this type of research is nearly unattainable; however, we diligently structured our search and selection process to encompass a broad spectrum of relevant studies, striving for comprehensive results to the best of our ability.
- **No extensive evaluation.** We have provided an initial validity assessment of the comprehensiveness of our dictionary, acknowledging the necessity for future empirical validation via controlled studies to supplement this preliminary study.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The main contribution of this study is the first version of a dictionary of emotional requirements based on the research literature for the healthcare and well-being domain. This helps stakeholders to establish a consistent understanding of emotional requirements to be addressed before they start designing a software-intensive system addressing some needs in this domain. Consequently, it ensures that the resulting system, effectively addresses emotional needs by the end users. We also learned that a common characteristic of emotional requirements in the healthcare and well-being domain is their low arousal and high valence.

Our future work will focus on complementing the initial dictionary presented in this paper with the emotional requirements elicited by identifying emotions relevant for healthcare and well-being from the literature on healthcare and health informatics. We also intend to explore how emotional requirements in healthcare and well-being can be matched with human values, as proposed by Schwartz [49], and previously studied in, for example, [50]. Furthermore, we will strengthen our first steps towards creating a dictionary of emotional requirements by studying how positive emotions can be purposefully constructed by applying information technology in the healthcare and well-being domain.

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